

IWSSPA

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON SOUND
SIGNAL PROCESSING APPLICATIONS 2024

Rota, Spain
July 2024

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON SOUND SIGNAL PROCESSING APPLICATIONS 2024
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Welcoming Note

General Co-Chair

Dr. Antonio J. Muñoz-Montoro
Universidad de Jaén, Spain

On behalf of the IWSSPA 2024 Organizing Committee, it is a genuine privilege to extend a warm welcome to you all to this momentous gathering, held as a satellite event of CMMSE 2024. The field of sound signal processing is undergoing a period of significant growth in both complexity and impact. This workshop provides a dynamic forum for the exchange of innovative research and insights.

The organization of an event of this magnitude necessitates the collective efforts of numerous individuals and organizations. First and foremost, we would like to express our sincerest gratitude to the authors who have taken the time to share their pioneering research with us. The condensation of months, or even years, of meticulous work

into concise, impactful presentations represents a significant challenge. Your dedication to advancing the field through thoughtful, well-structured contributions has established a foundation upon which we anticipate a fruitful exchange of ideas.

We would be remiss if we did not also acknowledge the indispensable contributions of our expert reviewers, who invested a great deal of time and expertise in the rigorous evaluation of submissions and the provision of invaluable feedback. The rigorous and high quality of our program are a direct result of your thoughtful assessments.

The success of this event would not have been possible without the generous support of our sponsors and institutional partners, who have demonstrated an unwavering commitment to fostering scientific exchange and innovation. Their contributions facilitate the provision of an enriching experience that encompasses both the theoretical and practical dimensions of sound signal processing.

In conclusion, the IWSSPA 2024 organizing team, in particular those responsible for logistical management, event promotion, and attendee hospitality, has provided invaluable support, ensuring the success of the event. Your dedication, enthusiasm, and collaborative spirit have been instrumental in making this workshop a reality. We extend our profound gratitude to all volunteers and local coordinators for their unwavering commitment to ensuring that every detail is meticulously perfected.

It is my hope that this collective endeavor will facilitate a dynamic exchange of ideas and foster connections, thereby laying the foundation for future advancements.

Conference Programme

TUESDAY, JULY 2

9:30 – 10:30 Registration

WEDNESDAY, JULY 3

Chairman: *Pedro Vera-Candeas*

Session time: 17:00 – 20:00

Location: Room 2

17:00 – 17:15 **ORCHESTRAL MUSIC SOURCE SEPARATION FOR MINUS-ONE APPLICATIONS**

David Diaz-Guerra, Tampere University

17:15 – 17:30 **PREDICTING ROOM IMPULSE RESPONSES THROUGH NEURAL NETWORKS**

Jose Antonio Belloch Rodríguez, Universitat Jaume I de Castellón

17:30 – 17:45 **ESTIMATION OF THE EARLY REVERBERATION FOR ROOM IMPULSE RESPONSE RECONSTRUCTION**

Mirco Pezzoli, Politecnico di Milano

17:45 – 17:00 **ACOUSTIC VIRTUAL SENSORS FOR INDUSTRIAL MONITORING USING NON-NEGATIVE MATRIX FACTORIZATION**

Maximo Cobos Serrano, Universitat de Valencia

18:00 – 18:15 **SYNCHRONIZING MEDIEVAL CHANT RECORDINGS WITH AN AUDIO-TO-SCORE ALIGNMENT SYSTEM**

Pedro Vera-Candeas, Universidad de Jaén

18:15 – 18:30 **A PYTHON TOOL FOR TIME-VARYING RIR DATASET GENERATION**

Marco Giordano, Università degli Studi dell'Aquila

Coffee break

19:00 – 19:15 **QUANTIFYING THE CORPUS BIAS PROBLEM IN AUTOMATIC MUSIC TRANSCRIPTION SYSTEMS**

Lukáš Marták, Johannes Kepler University Linz

19:15 – 19:30 **ACOUSTIC CAVITATION DETECTION THROUGH TRANSFER LEARNING**

Roberto Gil-Pita, Universidad de Alcalá

19:30 – 19:45 **ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMS RELATED TO REMOTE MONITORING OF SOUND IN INDUSTRIAL SCENARIOS**

Manuel Rosa Zurera, Universidad de Alcalá

19:45 – 20:00 **A DISTRIBUTED CLUSTERING METHOD FOR SPEECH ENHANCEMENT USING WIRELESS ACOUSTIC SENSOR NETWORKS**

Antonio Jesús Muñoz-Montoro, Universidad de Jaén

THURSDAY, JULY 4

16:00 – 17:00 **CMMSE POSTER SESSION**

At room 2

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Abstracts

*Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications
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Orchestral Music Source Separation for Minus-One Applications

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Abstract

Sound source separation is a classical problem in signal processing with different applications in different domains. When applied to music signals, one of the applications of being able to isolate the different instruments on a mixture is creating minus-one tracks with a target instrument removed, so music students can play the target instrument on top of it. We present and compare different approaches to generate these minus-one tracks for orchestral music using a state-of-the-art deep-learning separation model.

Key words: sound source separation, music source separation, minus-one, orchestral music

Extended abstract

1 Proposal and Methodology

In music source separation (MSS) systems, the input signal $x(t)$ is considered to be the sum of N sources $x(t) = \sum_n^N s_n(t)$, where $s_n(t)$ is the signal corresponding to the source n . Usually, the goal of MSS systems is to provide estimates $\hat{s}_m(t)$ of the target source signals but, in minus-one applications, our goal is to estimate the mixture of all the signals except the target signal m :

$$y_m(t) = \sum_n^{n \neq m} s_n(t). \quad (1)$$

If we have a deep learning model $\mathcal{M}_m^{Sep}$ trained to provide estimates of the target signal m , we can use it to estimate the minus-one mixtures by subtracting the estimated target signal from the original mixture:

$$\hat{y}_m^I(t) = x(t) - \hat{s}_m(t) = x(t) - \mathcal{M}_m^{Sep}\{x(t)\} \quad (2)$$

or by adding all the source estimates except from the target one:

$$\hat{y}_m^{II}(t) = \sum_n^{n \neq m} \hat{s}_n(t) = \sum_n^{n \neq m} \mathcal{M}_n^{Sep}\{x(t)\}. \quad (3)$$

Finally, we can also train the same model to directly estimate the minus-one mixtures $\mathcal{M}_m^{MO}$ instead of the separated signals, so the minus-one estimate is just the output of the model:

$$\hat{y}_m^{III}(t) = \mathcal{M}_m^{MO}\{x(t)\}. \quad (4)$$

In this contribution, we use the state-of-the-art model presented in [1] and the fourth version of the mueseval library [2,3] to compare these three approaches according to the signal-to-distortion ratios (SDR) of their minus-one estimates. The model takes the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) of a mono mixture as its input and estimates the spectral magnitude masks for every target instrument, using the mixture phase to reconstruct the time signal. In order to train the model we used SynthSOD, a synthetic dataset of orchestral music synthesized with the Spitfire BBC Symphony Orchestra synthesizer.

2 Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the resulting SDRs of the original mixture and the estimates computed with equations (2), (3), and (4). To obtain these results, we first computed the SDR on one-second frames and then computed the median value for every music piece (ignoring the frames where the target signal was silent) and finally computed the median over the music pieces (ignoring those where the target signal was not present). For a better analysis of the results, we also present the median SDRs for the ensemble pieces (up to 5 instruments) and for the orchestra pieces (more than 5 instruments) independently.

Evaluation on:	SynthSOD				Ensembles in SynthSOD				Orchestras in SynthSOD			
	Original	Approach I	Approach II	Approach III	Original	Approach I	Approach II	Approach III	Original	Approach I	Approach II	Approach III
Violin	12.26	16.84	11.77	15.78	6.11	14.33	10.74	13.37	16.54	18.22	12.06	17.35
Viola	9.93	14.24	10.88	13.07	7.22	13.79	10.13	12.48	11.56	14.59	11.12	13.93
Cello	4.27	10.64	5.58	10.35	-0.20	10.03	7.86	9.51	7.06	11.25	8.64	10.76
Bass	6.57	13.88	10.14	13.47	7.03	13.89	11.25	13.15	6.57	13.88	10.06	13.47
Flute	16.73	18.72	11.92	18.01	14.23	17.19	11.84	15.74	16.93	19.24	12.01	18.11
Clarinet	14.84	14.43	10.75	15.27	11.35	11.91	8.51	11.17	15.23	16.13	11.20	15.33
Oboe	13.66	18.14	11.94	16.94	8.12	15.15	10.41	14.12	15.25	18.72	12.18	17.70
Bassoon	14.97	16.12	11.78	15.43	8.60	12.07	10.55	10.30	15.81	16.52	12.05	15.97
Horn	15.62	15.97	10.90	14.17	44.98	12.85	9.44	11.34	17.73	17.41	11.47	15.82
Trumpet	5.40	10.57	9.19	10.52	0.15	9.12	6.22	9.55	8.87	13.05	10.18	13.13
Trombone	3.85	10.20	7.32	10.31	-0.33	8.32	5.66	9.13	13.68	13.58	8.79	13.89
Tuba	-0.05	2.85	4.61	3.10	-4.07	0.14	4.05	0.51	0.91	3.80	5.72	3.91
Harp	15.11	14.52	10.09	15.23	11.42	10.94	9.13	11.51	16.23	16.23	10.09	16.33
Timpani	21.51	22.32	11.95	22.08	21.36	23.76	7.84	22.35	21.53	21.81	12.02	21.61
Unt. perc.	24.39	25.90	10.55	25.19					24.39	24.39	10.55	25.19
MEAN	11.94	15.02	9.93	14.59	7.36	12.39	8.83	11.73	13.89	15.92	10.54	15.50

Table 1: Signal to distortion ratios [dB] for the original mixture and the minus-one estimates computed with the 3 proposed approaches.

We can see how the best results are obtained with the first proposed approach, i.e. subtracting the estimate of the target signal from the original mixture. The second approach obtains the worst results since it accumulates the artifacts of every estimate and the result ends up having a lower SDR than the input mixture. Training a model to directly estimate the minus-one mixtures performs slightly worse than the first approach, probably because the training is less efficient than when the target outputs are the individual instruments. We can also see how the SDR of the original mixture is higher in the orchestral pieces than in the ensemble pieces since the higher number of instruments makes every instrument more masked in the mixture, but the gains that we can obtain from our systems are lower since this makes the separation more difficult.

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Predicting Room Impulse Responses through Neural Networks

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Abstract

This work investigates the ability of deep neural networks (DNNs) to predict a specific room impulse response (RIR) [1, 2, 3] between two given room locations. We use three end-to-end deep learning (DL) models based on the encoder-decoder structure: an auto-encoder (AE), a variational AE (VAE) and a UNet. They try to generate a new RIR given:

1. The short-time Fourier transform (STFT) of a true RIR from the same room,
2. The spatial coordinates of the true and new RIRs
3. Other relevant room-related parameters.

On the one hand, the magnitude and phase of the STFT are computed and presented to the DNN input. On the other hand, the spatial coordinates and the room parameters form an information vector that is embedded into the DNNs through their latent space (AE, VAE) or equivalent layer (UNet). A real database of RIRs measured in five different rooms was used to train and test the models.

Two experiments have been carried out to study the influence of the magnitude and phase terms of the loss function on the performance of the models. An additional experiment investigated the ability of the DL models to generalize across rooms. Results show that the three DNNs are able to predict the magnitude of the STFT, but they cannot accurately predict its phase. When comparing their ability to generalize across spaces, the UNet achieves the best results.

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Estimation of the early reverberation for Room Impulse Response reconstruction

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Abstract

Parametric methods for sound field reconstruction are based on a compact signal model to represent an acoustic scene. Through the identification of the parameters of the model, the sound field is reconstructed in arbitrary locations. State-of-the-art parametric methods are limited to a simple signal model concerning the direct sound of the sources and a reverberant diffuse component. However, actual sound fields include strong (early) reverberation for which the diffuse assumption is not valid. In this work, we aim at extending parametric sound field reconstruction to model the contribution of early reverberation. The proposed methodology is based on an estimate of room impulse response from the signal acquired by a set of distributed higher order microphones. From the estimated room impulse response, the early reverberation is identified and modelled through virtual sources.

Key words: sound field reconstruction, early reverberation, room impulse response identification

Extended abstract

The problem of sound field reconstruction (SFR) from a limited number of distributed microphone acquisition is one of the main challenges in acoustic signal processing. SFR attracts an increasing interest due to its relevant applications in Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality where it enables the so-called *six degrees of freedom* (6DoF) interaction through which the user can move within a recorded sound scene perceiving the acoustic differences associated to the different locations. Different methodologies for SFR are available in the literature [1–5] that can be roughly classified in three categories: parametric, non-parametric and learning-based. In this work, we proposed an enhanced parametric model for SFR which overcomes one of the main limits of current methods [3]. In fact, the proposed method is able to estimate the early part of the room impulse response (RIR) and model the contribution of the reflections by means of virtual sources (VS). This provides a more complete model of the sound field removing the limitations to the simple *direct-diffuse* model adopted in the literature.

1 Proposal and Methodology

Let us assume a sound scene acquired by K Higher Order Microphones (HOM). The signals of each capsule is defined as $s_{m,k}(t)$, where $k = 1, \dots, K$ and $m = 1, \dots, M$ represent the HOM and capsule indexes, respectively and t is the time index. In addition, we assume that an approximation of the source signal $s_{src}(t)$ is known, e.g., measured by a microphone near the sound source. An estimate of the RIR from the source to each microphone can be obtained using a sliding time window to average

Figure 1: (a) Example of estimated and ground-truth RIR. (b) EDC for position $v = 1$. (c) NMSE values evaluated for all the $V = 100$ reconstructed RIRs.

the Generalized Cross Correlation (GCC) [6] between each $s_{m,k}$ and s_{src} . In order to identify the early reverberation in the estimated RIR, we model the signal by means of a sum of N Gaussian function as

$$g_{n,m,k}(t) = a_{n,m,k} \exp\left(-\frac{(t - \tau_{n,m,k})^2}{2\sigma_{n,m,k}^2}\right), \quad (1)$$

where $a_{n,m,k}$, $\tau_{n,m,k}$ are the amplitude and time delay associated to the n -th reflection, respectively, and $\sigma_{n,m,k}$ is the standard deviation of the n -th Gaussian function. The N reflections are thus localized at each HOM by computing the direction of arrival (DOA) of each Gaussian function using a delay-and-sum beamformer [7]. Thanks to the knowledge of DOAs and time delays (1), the position of the N VS generating the reverberation is obtained through combinatorial optimization [8]. Finally, the RIRs can be resynthesized at a given point $\mathbf{r}_v$, $v = 1, \dots, V$, as a weighted sum of VS

$$h(t, \mathbf{r}_v) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n \delta(t - \tau_n(\mathbf{r}_v)), \quad (2)$$

where a_n is the reflection coefficient of the n -th VS found from the joint optimization with the VS location and $\tau_n(\mathbf{r}_v)$ is the delay associated to distance travelled by the wave fronts from the VS position to the target location $\mathbf{r}_v$.

2 Results and Discussion

We tested the method using $K = 4$ HOMs with $M = 8$ capsules and radius $R = 2.5$ cm. The RIRs has been simulated using the image-source method [9] with a room of $14 \times 6 \times 3$ m. For simplicity, we set the reflection order of the RIR to 1 thus obtaining $N = 6$ reflections while the reflection coefficient of the walls is set to $a = 0.9$. The performance of the method is evaluated in $V = 100$ positions in terms of the Energy Decay Curve (EDC) of the RIR and Normalized Mean Squared Error (NMSE) between the actual RIR and the estimated ones. In Fig. 1(a) an example of estimated RIR is depicted with the reference one. Observing the EDC in Fig. 1(b), we can notice that the estimated RIR follows the energy trend of the reference, obtaining an accurate reconstruction of the RIR. This result is confirmed by the NMSE in Fig. 1(c) for which we obtained an average value of -54 dB.

Overall, this preliminary evaluation shows promising result in reconstructing the early part of the reverberation through the use of VS and estimated RIRs. Further works include the embedding of this method within a complete parametric framework along with the direct and diffuse sound estimation and the evaluation of the proposed method on real measurements and scenarios with multiple acoustic sources.

Acknowledgments

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Acoustic Virtual Sensors for Industrial Monitoring using Non-negative Matrix Factorization

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Abstract

This paper introduces the concept of using Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) activations of sound spectrograms as virtual sensors for industrial monitoring. The proposed method focuses on capturing and analyzing acoustic signals in industrial environments to monitor relevant parts of industrial processes. By utilizing NMF, we can decompose acoustic signals into meaningful components, enabling the detection of specific events and conditions within the monitored processes. The method's effectiveness is demonstrated through experimental results, showing its potential to enhance industrial process monitoring and optimization.

Key words: industrial monitoring, non-negative matrix factorization, virtual sensors, audio

Extended abstract

1 Proposal and Methodology

In industrial settings, the need for effective monitoring and control of processes is paramount. Traditional physical sensors are often used to measure various parameters such as temperature, pressure, and vibration. However, deploying a large number of physical sensors can be costly and impractical. As an alternative, we propose the use of virtual sensors [1] based on acoustic signal analysis. These virtual sensors leverage Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) [2] to extract relevant features from the captured sound, providing a cost-effective and versatile solution for monitoring industrial processes. The use of acoustic signals for monitoring industrial processes is not entirely new. Previous research has explored various techniques for sound-based anomaly detection and process monitoring [3, 4]. While NMF has been widely used in audio signal processing tasks, particularly in music source separation [5, 6, 7, 8, 9] and speech enhancement [10, 11], the idea of using NMF activations as virtual sensors for industrial monitoring has not been extensively explored. This work aims to fill this gap by proposing a detailed methodology for implementing virtual sensors using NMF, providing a comprehensive framework for acoustic-based industrial monitoring.

Consider an input mel-scale spectrogram of a full manufacturing cycle $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{F \times T}$, with F frequency bands and T time frames. NMF aims to factorize $\mathbf{V}$ into two non-negative matrices: the basis matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{F \times K}$ and the activation matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{K \times T}$, i.e. $\mathbf{V} \approx \mathbf{WH}$, where K is the number of components.

The factorization is achieved by minimizing a divergence function $D(\mathbf{V}, \hat{\mathbf{V}})$, typically selected as the Euclidean distance or the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence. The solution is usually obtained via an iterative alternating update algorithm employing multiplicative update rules based on a gradient descent approach. Additionally, sparsity constraints affecting both $\mathbf{W}$ and $\mathbf{H}$ are commonly applied to enable meaningful spectral patterns related to different acoustic sources.

The application of the proposed virtual sensor system was demonstrated on a plastic injection molding machine. This type of machine is widely used in manufacturing industries to produce plastic parts by injecting molten plastic material into a mold. The machine undergoes several operational phases, including material loading, mold closing, injection, cooling, and mold opening. Each phase generates distinct acoustic signatures, making it an ideal candidate for acoustic-based monitoring. The microphone captured sounds during various operational phases over multiple production cycles to ensure a comprehensive dataset. The data acquisition system was set up to record audio signals at a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz, ensuring high fidelity and capturing the full range of acoustic frequencies produced by the machine. We analyzed a total of 4 hours of audio recordings, properly segmented into different manufacturing cycles, applying NMF to each of them with $K = 10$ components. To this end, we calculated mel spectrograms with $F = 128$ frequency bands, and a varying number of T frames per audio recording. To ensure the robustness and relevance of the spectral bases, we employed a clustering technique to group similar basis vectors. This step helps in selecting a representative set of spectral bases that capture the essential characteristics of the acoustic signals associated with different operational phases. We used the k -means clustering algorithm to group the basis vectors obtained from the NMF decomposition, partitioning all the basis vectors from the dataset into $k = 10$ clusters by minimizing the within-cluster variance. After clustering, the centroid of each cluster is selected as the representative spectral basis. The activation matrix $\mathbf{H}$ is then recalculated using the selected cluster representatives $\mathbf{c}_i \in \mathbb{R}_+^{F \times 1}$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, k - 1$, ensuring that the virtual sensors are based on a robust set of spectral bases. The concept of virtual sensors involves using the rows of the activation matrix as indicators of specific acoustic events or conditions within the industrial process. Each row represents the temporal activation of a particular basis, capturing presence and intensity of specific acoustic patterns over time.

2 Results and Discussion

To validate the proposed approach, a validation dataset was created with manually annotated phases of the machine's operation. The annotations were based on expert observations and served as the ground truth for evaluating the correlation between the NMF activations and the actual operational phases. The activation matrix $\mathbf{H}$ obtained from the NMF decomposition was compared against the manual annotations using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The correlation analysis showed high positive correlations between the NMF activations and the manually annotated phases. Specifically, the average Pearson correlation coefficient across all phases was found to be $r = 0.85$ ($p < 0.01$), indicating a strong linear relationship between the NMF activations and the machine's operational phases. This demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of using NMF activations as virtual sensors for industrial monitoring. The proposed method leverages the rich information contained in acoustic signals to monitor and analyze the operational state of industrial machinery. The experimental results show that the system can effectively identify different operational phases. By monitoring these activations in real-time, we can infer the operational state of the machine, potentially detecting anomalies or significant changes in the process. For instance, a sudden change in the activation pattern may indicate a mechanical fault or a deviation from normal operating conditions.

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Synchronizing Medieval Chant Recordings with an Audio-to-Score Alignment System

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Abstract

For over a century, scholars have systematically studied medieval music. Today, extensive databases containing Gregorian chant transcriptions in GABC format are available, often supplemented with images of original manuscripts and audio recordings. This paper introduces an audio-to-score alignment system designed to synchronize GABC format chants with their corresponding audio renditions. The system first converts the GABC score into MIDI, taking into account tempo and note duration markers such as punctum mora and episema. The MIDI score is then aligned with the audio by calculating a full pairwise distance matrix between the audio and score sequences and employing an efficient offline Dynamic Time Warping algorithm. This process assigns precise timestamps to each square note and its corresponding Latin syllable in the audio performance. Our system demonstrates robust resilience to variations in tempo and note duration, though it is not applicable to unison chants.

Key words: score alignment, Gregorian chants, Dynamic Time Warping

Extended abstract

1 Proposal and Methodology

In this paper, we introduce an audio-to-score alignment system aimed at synchronizing chants in GABC format with their corresponding audio representations. Our approach adapts the algorithm from [1], which was initially developed for classical music. The process begins by converting the GABC score into MIDI format, accounting for predefined tempo and note duration values. We then align the MIDI score with the audio by computing a pairwise distance matrix between the audio and score sequences. Utilizing an efficient version of offline Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), our method optimizes memory and CPU usage. This algorithm precisely times each square-note within the audio performance.

2 Results and Discussion

We evaluated our method using five manually annotated chant recordings from the Neumz application. These recordings feature high-quality performances by the nuns of the Abbey of Notre-Dame de Fidélité of Jouques, captured live in the Abbey with some reverberation and ambient noise, occasionally accompanied by an organ. The chants tested include: 'Quando natus est' (4 minutes), 'Exsurge Domine fer opem' (3.5 minutes), 'Urbs Jerusalem beata' (3 minutes), 'Voce[m] jucunditatis' (4 minutes), and 'Regem Confessorum Dominum' (7 minutes). The annotations consist of a list of verse lines, each associated with a specific point in the audio. Consequently, we could only assess the alignment of the verses, despite our method operating at the note level. We calculated alignment accuracy as the percentage of verses that deviated less than a defined threshold (or tolerance window) from the reference alignment.

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A Python Tool for Time-varying RIR Dataset Generation

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Abstract

In this work we propose an optimized and versatile Python pipeline for the synthesis of time-varying RIR (Room Impulse Response) datasets, obtained through spatio-temporal sampling of complex trajectories inside well-characterized virtual enclosed spaces. This solution has been effectively tested for simulating walking trajectories applied to speech signals at a controlled speed (around 0.84m/s inside an enclosed space simulation). Our solution shows promise in both extending the simulation capabilities of existing frameworks (which currently provide fixed RIR convolution only) and serving as a new generative Python API for synthetic yet realistic datasets.

Key words: Room Acoustics, Room Impulse Response (RIR), Python, Time-varying Convolution

Extended abstract

State-of-The-Art & Methodology: we conducted an initial survey about RIR synthesis tools [2, 6, 7, 14], reference datasets [15, 16, 18], and time-varying convolution techniques [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13]. Almost all software solutions here examined rely on the same computational model for Virtual Sound Sources (VSSs) simulation, associated with sound reflection/absorption outcomes: the Image-Source Model (ISM) [1].

PyRoomAcoustics (PRA) [2] stands out as the most comprehensive Python scripting API, integrating most of the aspects of environmental characterization. It includes: per surface absorption patterns, air temperature and density, irregular and regular (ShoeBox) perimeters, multiple microphone setups (monaural, binaural, and arbitrary multi-loudspeaker virtualizations), and multi-VSS placement definitions. Wayverb [7] offers similar features with hybrid (waveguide) modeling approach for low frequencies, being restricted to specific operating systems (MacOS ≥ 10.11) and to NVIDIA GPUs availability for accelerated RIR estimate. Unlike PRA, Wayverb is released as a pre-compiled GUI standalone (no scripting API) and lacks of import compatibility with room mesh specifications from 3D files (e.g.: `.obj`, `.stl`). `gpu-RIR` [6] can be considered a simplified PRA re-implementation with GPU acceleration, but supports simplified ShoeBox cases only. Furthermore, with some scripting effort it seems possible to integrate PRA simulations by incorporating physical obstacles inside virtual rooms [17].

None of these tools actually integrate Time-Varying Convolution (TVC) computation. Following [8, 9, 10, 11, 12], we tested a “sliding” approach to convolution in the time-domain updating RIR buffer content at each VSS and optimizing it with Just-in-Time (JIT) compilation [19]. However, unlike Head-Related Impulse Responses (HRIRs) that are always the same in size, RIRs can significantly vary in length, due to room resonance modes, standing waves, etc. As a result, convolution outputs were characterized by audible artifacts and were perceptively unconvincing, even using a 3rd order spline interpolation technique. Furthermore, although we are not interested in a real-time solution, we consider computational efficiency as crucial because generating a sufficiently large dataset may require the rendering of thousands of VSS-related RIRs.

Our Proposal, Results & Discussion: we decided to develop a set of functions to perform TVC computation of spatio-temporal trajectories of a virtual source, relying on PRA framework and maintaining a high degree of compatibility with Wayverb.

We defined two types of trajectory segments for an audio source: *rectilinear* and *curved*, interpolating an arc of a circle between given `start` and `stop` spatial coordinates (in meters). Complex trajectories can be generated by joining segments in a suitable way. Both functions accepts the following parameters: `sampling_interval` (in sec.), `tot_duration` (in sec.), and `speed` (in m/s), with the last parameter possibly adjusted according to the `sampling_interval` and the `duration` of the audio file. The circumference interpolation follows an arbitrary user-specified `radius`: if too small, the arch will be interpolated with the minimum consistent radius.

The input file `sample_rate` (SR) rules the overall simulation. Materials absorption coefficients can be chosen among those already available in PRA or specified accordingly. The most important parameter is `order`, which sets the limit of the exponential number of computed image sources for each RIR: preliminary listening tests have shown that the 12th order seems to produce a sufficiently convincing amount of reflections, requiring computational *wall-time* of about 6min at a SR of 44.1KHz for a simple (but irregular) room shape.

The trajectory applied to the audio file is thus sampled, according to the spatial sampling parameters, and for each point a VSS is placed and the related RIR is computed. We provide *monaural* and *binaural* microphones simplified placing but opting for a generalized Room definition, it is possible to define any arbitrary recording set-up, specifying `azimuth`, `colatitude`, and `directivity_pattern` for each microphone.

The TVC is implemented in the frequency domain, following this routine: (1) compute the list of N RIRs related to the N VSS and then the convolution with the input signal via complex multiplication of their DFT; (2) apply *causal* zero-padding to each convolution output, so as to match the nearest multiple of the trajectory’s `sampling_interval`, here used as framing size; (3) The overall TVC output is obtained as a *frame-wise* sum of the convolutions computed in each sampling point, applying a linearly decreasing amplitude envelope to the output frame of the previous point and a linearly increasing one to the output frame of the subsequent point.

With a sufficiently dense spatio-temporal sampling (e.g.: 0.01sec.), the output encodes the complete trajectory, inducing the perception of a speaker moving at a constant speed. An entire dataset synthesis process can be scripted by encoding all previous parameters in multiple `.json` files, which can be parsed and linked to a unique or different audio files. Examples and (documented) scripts, are available in our GitHub repository.

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Quantifying the Corpus Bias Problem in Automatic Music Transcription Systems

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Abstract

Automatic Music Transcription (AMT) is the task of recognizing notes in audio recordings of music. The State-of-the-Art (SotA) benchmarks have been dominated by deep learning systems. Due to the scarcity of high quality data, they are usually trained and evaluated exclusively or predominantly on classical piano music. Unfortunately, that hinders our ability to understand how they generalize to other music. Previous works have revealed several aspects of memorization and overfitting in these systems. We identify two primary sources of distribution shift: the music, and the sound. Complementing recent results on the sound axis (i.e. acoustics, timbre), we investigate the musical one (i.e. note combinations, dynamics, genre). We evaluate the performance of several SotA AMT systems on two new experimental test sets which we carefully construct to emulate different levels of musical distribution shift. Our results reveal a stark performance gap, shedding further light on the Corpus Bias problem, and the extent to which it continues to trouble these systems.

Key words: automatic music transcription, polyphonic piano music, note entanglement, corpus bias, musical distribution shift, evaluation benchmark, out-of-distribution inference, robustness.

1 Motivation and Goals

In the past decade, the state of the art in Automatic Music Transcription (AMT) has been repeatedly improved by deploying various Deep Neural Network (DNN) architectures, trained to perform the task in an end-to-end manner [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. Earlier work has shown a tendency of such systems to memorize observed note combinations, hindering their ability to recognize new ones – called the *entanglement problem* [9]. More recently, the lasting presence of the issue has been observed on a slightly larger scale, denoted as *corpus bias* in [10]. Furthermore, overfitting on sound-related properties of the training data seems to also diminish performance of these systems on out-of-distribution (OOD) data [11, 12, 13]. We evaluate a set of DNN-based SotA AMT systems, which were trained exclusively on classical music (mostly from MAESTRO [11]). We name these OaF [4], Kong [6], T5 [7], Toyama [8], and Edwards [12] in the following. Using a new, highly curated test corpus recorded under uniform *sound* conditions, we contribute new evidence towards the question of AMT performance degradation in the presence of *musical* distribution shift. To support reproducibility, we make our resources available.¹

*Equal contribution.

¹https://github.com/CPJKU/musical_distribution_shift

2 Methodology

To produce data for AMT evaluation, we first collect MIDI files and then synthesize them on a real piano, obtaining ground truth note alignments. In order to eliminate the confounding effects of differences in sound, we construct our corpus by recording automated performances of our MIDI targets on a Yamaha Disklavier grand piano, same as in [13]. This ensures fixed but realistic timbre, acoustics, and recording conditions of studio quality. We start by curating two sub-sets: (1) Genre, and (2) Random.

The Genre set (1) comprises piano performances of pieces from 10 different genres, only one of them being classical music, to investigate the possible effect of this high-level variable on AMT performance. We source pieces from the ADL Piano MIDI dataset [14] as follows: discard pieces containing > 5 sec of silence or falling outside the range of 2 – 3 min duration, and choose 5 pieces per genre at random.

The Random set (2) is synthesized to emulate *extreme* distribution shift, far outside the realm of what a human would call *musical*. It comprises 24×3 sequences, each 2 minutes long, maintaining a given polyphony degree $p \in \{1, \dots, 24\}$, and a dynamics range $d \in \{0 : [60 - 68], 1 : [32 - 96], 2 : [1 - 127]\}$. The p polyphonic streams are filled with note sequences of randomly sampled pitch $\sim U(21, 108)$, velocity $\sim U(d_{\min}, d_{\max})$, and duration $\sim \text{Beta}(\alpha = 2, \beta = 5)$ between $[0.01 - 5.00]$ seconds. It differs from the RAND subset of MAPS [15] mainly by randomizing and de-correlating onsets and durations of notes, but also by containing higher polyphony degrees and extra range of dynamics.

3 Results and Discussion

We run the systems to transcribe the audio, and report note-level performance by model and data slice in Figure 1. The left plot compares the five models on the different genre test sets (5 pieces per genre; error bars show 50% confidence intervals). On the right side, we show the performance of each model at different polyphony degrees, averaged over the 3 levels of dynamics, with data bands showing inter-quartile ranges. The black dashed line gives a rough reference point for average performance across these models on the (in-distribution) MAESTRO test set.² Most notably, we observe a clear, and partly dramatic, decrease in performance as we go from Classical to other test genres (Fig. 1, left). Performance on random notes (right) tends to be even worse. This demonstrates a strong genre bias effect; in view of this result, performance numbers given in the literature must be interpreted with care.

Figure 1: The Musical OOD performance of SotA systems (Note F1 with Onset, Offset and Velocity).

²The metrics are from the original papers, so the sound distribution for this line is MAESTRO, not ours. We plan to quantify this effect by experiments with (parts of) MAESTRO re-recorded on our piano.

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Acoustic Cavitation Detection Through Transfer Learning

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Abstract

Cavitation noise impacts the performance and durability of hydraulic machinery, causing material erosion, efficiency loss, and mechanical failure. Early detection is crucial to prevent costly downtime. Traditional methods lack real-time precision, prompting the use of microphones to capture acoustic emissions from cavitation events. Advanced signal processing and deep learning techniques improve detection accuracy.

This study utilizes transfer learning with the YAMNet pre-trained network for cavitation detection in hydraulic systems. YAMNet, based on MobileNetV1, is adapted for binary classification by varying the number of network layers to balance performance and computational cost. Experiments conducted with a comprehensive database of hydraulic system recordings, including various noise sources and cavitation sounds, demonstrate that using the first 40 and 46 layers of YAMNet yields optimal results. This approach outperforms traditional feature extraction and logistic regression methods, showcasing the effectiveness of transfer learning in enhancing cavitation detection and maintaining hydraulic machinery.

Key words: Transfer Learning, Cavitation detection, Hydraulic System

Extended abstract

Cavitation noise affects the performance and durability of hydraulic machinery, causing erosion, reduced efficiency, and mechanical failure [1]. Early detection is crucial for maintaining machinery and preventing downtime, but traditional methods often lack real-time precision [2]. Using microphones to capture acoustic emissions from cavitation events offers a non-invasive solution [3]. Advanced signal processing and deep learning techniques, like pre-trained networks such as AlexNet, analyze these emissions to accurately detect and diagnose cavitation noise [4]. This enhances real-time monitoring, improves predictive maintenance, and ensures efficient machinery operation.

This paper explores using transfer learning with audible signals to detect cavitation in a hydraulic system. We employ the YAMNet (Yet Another Mobile-Net) pre-trained network, based on the MobileNetV1 architecture and trained on the AudioSet dataset [5]. YAMNet's depth-wise separable convolutions reduce model size and complexity, making it suitable for mobile and real-time applications.

A novel aspect of our approach is controlling the number of layers in the network by selecting only the first L layers of YAMNet. This segmentation allows us to balance performance and computational

Figure 1: Diagram of the hydraulic system (left), and P_D vs. P_{FA} for the classifiers described in the paper (right).

cost. By examining different network configurations, we aim to correlate network depth with detection effectiveness, optimizing performance while minimizing resource usage.

In our experiments, we created a comprehensive database of recordings from a hydraulic system. The scaled diagram of the system (Figure 1, left) shows various noise sources in green, including a fan, a pneumatic valve, a motorized valve, two non-return valves, and two pumps. Cavitation sound sources, primarily at the pipe elbows where cavitation is more likely, are marked in red. The position of the microphone used for detecting cavitation is indicated in blue.

Using this setup, we recorded 4600 seconds of data with a SCADA system automating various machinery configurations. During part of these experiments, the pumps and valves were adjusted to induce cavitation. The recordings included 2061 seconds of pump noises, 34 seconds of non-return valve activation noises, 673 seconds of pneumatic valve sounds, 495 seconds of motorized valve sounds, 237 seconds of fan sounds, 460 seconds of human activity, and 255 seconds of cavitation sounds. These recordings were artificially combined to create noisy scenarios, resulting in an extended database of 31496 seconds with audio features extracted every 0.48 seconds, producing 62992 patterns. Among these, 2730 patterns contained cavitation sounds, representing 4.3% of the total. The database was divided into five folds, ensuring diverse noise inclusion in each fold, and a 5-fold cross-validation process was employed.

We varied the number of layers in YAMNet from 28 to 82 in increments of 6 layers, fine-tuning the network weights using the Adam training algorithm for 10 epochs. Three folds of the database were used for training, one for monitoring and early stopping, and one for testing the detector. Figure 1 (right) shows the results in terms of P_D (probability of detecting cavitation) versus P_{FA} (probability of false alarms) for different YAMNet configurations. For comparison, results using a classical feature extraction approach combined with logistic regression are also included. The transfer learning approach with the first 40 and 46 layers of YAMNet (networks with 64 and 77 MFLOPS, respectively) yielded the best results, making these configurations optimal for cavitation detection using microphones.

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Analysis of problems related to remote monitoring of sound in industrial scenarios

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Abstract

This paper deals with an analysis of the characteristics of sounds recorded in industrial environments, that makes anomaly detection difficult. For anomaly detection to be implemented, the detector must be fed with signals emitted by the machine under study, isolated from other sounds in the environment. Sound separation can be implemented in the time domain if sounds are not simultaneous, in the frequency domain, if the energy appears in different bands for the different machines, or by spatial filtering if they are produced in different places. Unfortunately, the nature of signals makes this process difficult, motivating the research to get very accurate classifiers, and multiband microphone arrays with narrow main lobes, and high difference between the main beam level and the highest sidelobe level.

Key words: Predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, remote monitoring, sound

Extended abstract

Anomaly detection is a research topic where sensor technology, signal processing, and data science are applied [1]. The development of the Internet of Things (IoT), the explosive growth of big data and machine learning techniques, and the important applications where it can be applied, have all together motivated the current interest in this topic. Anomaly detection can be applied to very different issues: medical applications, sports, behavioural biometrics, elderly care, robotics, arts and entertainment, smart surveillance, gesture and posture analysis, among others [2].

Many anomaly detection algorithms use the information acquired with different types of sensors, mainly cameras and acoustic sensors, but some others, such as inertial sensors or wearable sensors can be used. Acoustic monitoring allows the detection, location and tracking of sound events and sources, generating an exhaustive knowledge of the sound scene. This analysis helps not only to monitor activity, but also to detect anomalies occurring in the scene. Both, sound event detection and acoustic scene classification are techniques of perceiving the environment or situation [3], and can be successfully applied to predictive maintenance in the industry [4].

This paper deals with the analysis of the main problems that arise when obtaining acoustic signals for anomaly detection in industrial environments. Acoustic monitoring to detect anomalies in machine

operation in industry, can be carried out in several ways. For example, microphones dedicated exclusively to monitoring individual machines can be used, or arrays of microphones can be used to remotely monitor the entire scene [5, 6, 7]. In the later approach, algorithms for sound source separation must be applied, to isolate the signal of interest from the remaining, prior to the application of anomaly detection algorithms. The sound source separation can be implemented in different ways. If only one sound source is present in the time interval considered, separation can be carried out by a simple windowing process in time. The system must rely on the results of an accurate detection of the number of sources, and a precise sound classifier, to detect the time intervals of each non-simultaneous source. When sources concentrate energy in very different bands, frequency filtering can be applied. If there is more than one sound event simultaneously, spatial filtering algorithms (array processing) can be applied for spatial source separation with modern techniques [8]. For the application of spatial filtering, it is desirable to have a narrow main beam, which is achieved with a large array aperture (high number of microphones and high microphone spacing).

To illustrate the difficulties encountered in practice, the following figures depict on the one hand, the power spectral of sound signals, showing the large variation of frequency bands of emission. If spatial filters are to be applied, and the difference in signals levels is greater than the difference between the main beam level and the highest sidelobe level, it is very possible that interferences appear from the sidelobes to the main beam with higher energy than that of the target signal. Figure 1 shows these problems for real signals in an industrial environment. This problem motivates research into multiband microphone arrays.

Figure 1: Energy calculated in segments of 32ms length of different machines (left), and power spectra of three machines, showing the large variation in frequency band of sound emission (right)

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A distributed clustering method for speech enhancement using wireless acoustic sensor networks

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Abstract

Speech enhancement in noisy environments remains a significant challenge, exacerbated by the detrimental effects of reverberation and noise. While existing methods have addressed this issue, the emergence of wireless acoustic sensor networks (WASNs) offers a promising solution by exploiting spatial information to mitigate acoustic distortions. In this study, we propose a framework for speech enhancement in noisy environments using WASNs. The proposal consists of two steps. First, a rank estimation approach is used to estimate the number of speakers present in the acoustic scene. Then, an unsupervised clustering method based on magnitude-squared coherence estimation and non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) is used to cluster microphone nodes into subnetworks associated with different speakers. To address the challenges of scalability and computational complexity, a distributed approach is introduced in which a group of sensor nodes performs local processing and collaboratively exchanges information with neighboring nodes to form subnetworks. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed framework in classifying nodes into subnetworks based on microphone observations, yielding promising results.

Key words: WASN, node clustering, coherence, NMF, distributed processing, confusion matrix

Extended abstract

1 Proposal and Methodology

In this paper, we present a framework capable of estimating the number of speakers present in an acoustic scene and subsequently clustering the microphones distributed throughout the scene based on these identified sources. The framework comprises three main steps. First, speaker number estimation is performed using the RESURE algorithm[1]. Next, following a similar approach to [2], the Spectral Magnitude-Squared Coherence is calculated between each pair of microphones, resulting in a non-negative matrix. This matrix is then factorized in the third phase using a non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) approach [3], enabling the clustering of the microphones.

Additionally, this work proposes a method for distributed clustering, wherein it is assumed that not all audio recordings are available to compute the coherence for all microphone pairs. To address this, certain cells in the matrix are disabled before performing NMF analysis.

2 Results and Discussion

Speech signals were taken from the CHiME corpus [4], and noise signals were extracted from the AURORA database [5]. The noise signals included babble and factory noise (SNR = 10 dB). The mixing conditions were simulated in a rectangular room of $10\text{m} \times 10\text{m} \times 3\text{m}$, with reverberation times of 200 ms and 400 ms. Fifty microphones were randomly placed in the room, and the number of speakers was either 4 or 5, also randomly located within the room.

Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed framework in estimating the number of speakers and classifying nodes into subnetworks based on microphone observations. The framework yielded promising and robust results regardless of the type of noise used in the mixture, with only a slight degradation observed when the reverberation time increased.

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Application of Quantum Machine Learning for Detection of Adventitious Respiratory Sounds

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Abstract

Respiratory diseases represent a significant challenge within the global healthcare landscape, contributing to high mortality rates. Early detection and timely intervention are crucial in managing these conditions effectively, reducing the need for more complex and expensive treatments at advanced stages.

The complexity of diagnosing respiratory diseases has driven researchers to adopt advanced technologies, particularly in the realms of signal processing and artificial intelligence (AI). These technologies facilitate the automated classification and analysis of respiratory sounds. AI techniques, including machine learning and deep learning, have shown considerable promise in identifying patterns and anomalies in respiratory sounds, leading to more reliable and efficient diagnostic processes.

In recent years, the advent of Quantum Computing has opened new avenues in the field of AI, specifically through Quantum Machine Learning (QML) techniques [1, 2]. Thus, we have applied a suite of quantum algorithms to a variety of databases containing respiratory and cardiovascular sounds [3, 4], using a novel Python package for Quantum Machine Learning, LazyQML [5]. In this research, we have found that QML models may outperform their classical counterparts in environments with low quality data data, such as in biomedical applications, particularly in health sound classification problems.

This discovery is significant because biomedical data, especially in fields like respiratory and cardiovascular health, often contain a high degree of variability and reduced information. Traditional machine learning models can struggle with such data, as they typically require extensive preprocessing and cleaning to perform accurately. Quantum Machine Learning models, however, have shown a remarkable resilience to these issues, offering superior performance in some cases where data quality cannot be guaranteed [6].

In our experiments, QML models demonstrated a higher tolerance for missing, incomplete, or inconsistent data, leading to more reliable and robust classifications of health sounds. This robustness makes QML particularly well-suited for real-world biomedical applications, where obtaining perfectly clean data is often impractical. The ability of QML to handle effectively this kind of data could lead to more accurate diagnostics and better patient outcomes.

Key words: Audio Processing, Quantum Machine Learning, Healthcare Applications

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